

**RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED CLINICAL STUDY TO EVALUATE
THE EFFICACY OF JWARAHARA MAHAKASHAYA AS GUDAVARTI
IN JWARASANTAPA W.S.R TO PYREXIA IN CHILDREN**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Fever in children accounts for 70% of presenting complaints in the pediatric practices. Even though fever has some benefits like, stimulating the body's defense mechanism, it can also lead to medical complications in young children. In treating the cases of fever, palatability of *Jwarahara Dravyas* has been one of the prime reasons for the lesser proliferation of *Ayurvedic* drugs in pediatric age group. The efficacy of *Jwarahara* drugs administered orally is well known, however when administered parenterally specifically through rectal route was less tested, which presently is the need for the day. Hence, this study aims to evaluate the efficacy of *Jwarahara Mahakashaya* as *Gudavarti*, in the management of *Jwarasantapa* (Pyrexia) in children. **Methods:** 30 subjects(2-5years) who were diagnosed with *Jwarasantapa* (Pyrexia) were randomly selected. They were divided into two groups of 15 subjects each. Group A was administered with *Jwarahara Mahakashaya Gudavarti* and Group B was administered with

Amrutottara Kashaya Gudavarti. Assessment was done at regular interval ie. before

treatment, 30 minutes, 60 minutes, 120 minutes & 180 minutes after the administration of *Gudavarti*, based on the subjective and objective parameters and graded accordingly.

Observations & Results: Both medicines were found to be effective within the groups with highly significant P value. On comparing the efficacy of treatment between the group, *Jwarahara Mahakashya Gudavarti* showed better results in *Jwarasantapa*. **Discussion:** *Jwarahara Mahakashya Gudavarti* and *Amrutottara Kashaya Gudavarti* with its potential *Doshahara* (alleviation of Doshas) action along with various phytochemical properties showed significant reduction of *Jwarasantapa* (pyrexia) in both the groups. *Jwarahara Mahakashya Gudavarti* had sustained action on *Jwarasantapa* up to 180 minutes of treatment. **Conclusion:** The efficacy of *Jwarahara Mahakashya Gudavarti* was greater than that of *Amrutottara Kashaya Gudavarti* in *Jwarasantapa* w.s.r to pyrexia in children.

KEYWORDS: *Jwarasantapa*; Pyrexia in children; *Gudavarti*; *Jwarahara Mahakashya Gudavarti*; *Amrutottara Kashaya Gudavarti*.

1. INTRODUCTION

Children under the age group 5 years have an immature immune system, therefore when exposed to the outside environment more often, they become vulnerable to being ill. Data reveals that, in low and middle-income countries, children under the age of 5, have 2-9 febrile episodes in a year with an average of 5.88 episodes (**Costing of febrile illness among under five children, 2019**).^[1] Even though a symptom like fever has many benefits like, stimulating the body's defence mechanism, inhibition of infection, etc, it can also lead to medical complexities in children. The most common complication of fever in children below five years is febrile seizures, its peak incidence is on 2-3 years of age and can lead to irreversible organ damage (**Febrile seizure, 2017**).^[2]

Jwara is most important among all diseases because it affects the *Deha* (Body), *Indriya* (Sense organs) and *Manas* (Mind) (**Charaka Sutra 3/4**).^[3] The *Jwarahara Mahakashya* explained in *Charaka Samhita* (**Charaka Chikitsa 4/39**)^[4] can be used in all *Jwaras* irrespective of the condition. The palatability is one of the prime reasons for the lesser proliferation of *Ayurvedic* drugs that are administered orally, exploring alternative route of administration of these drugs is the need for the day. Rectal suppositories are widely used in the modern system of medicines to effectively treat fever related emergencies in children as it has a quicker action because of the direct systemic effect. The concept of *Vartis* in *Ayurvedic* classics have been well explained, however its uses are very limited. Since oral

administration of *Jwarahara Dravya* is a great challenge among children with febrile illness, the administration of *Jwarahara Dravya* in the form of *Gudavarti* is a novel technique. Hence the present clinical study was planned as an innovative way to evaluate the efficacy of *Jwarahara Mahakashaya* as *Gudavarti* in *Jwarasantapa*.

AIM

- To evaluate the efficacy of *Jwarahara Mahakashaya Gudavarti* in *Jwarasantapa*.

OBJECTIVES

Primary - To evaluate the efficacy of *Jwarahara Mahakashaya Gudavarti* in *Jwarasantapa* by employing standard validated scales. (GRASP fever chart)

Secondary

- To evaluate the efficacy of *Amrutottara Kashaya (Sahasrayogam 1/6)*^[5] as *Gudavarti* in *Jwarasantapa* by employing standard validated scales (GRASP fever chart).
- To compare the efficacy of *Jwarahara Mahakashaya Gudavarti* with *Amrutottara Kashaya Gudavarti* in *Jwarasantapa* by employing standard validated scales. (**GRASP fever chart, 2018**).^[6]

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Research design

- **Study Design:** Randomized controlled clinical study.
- **Number of groups:** Two
- **Source of data:** Subjects were selected from the Research Institute who fulfilled the inclusion criteria and whose parents were willing to give consent were selected for the study.
- **Sample size:** Total number of patients -30, each group (Group A and Group B) consisting of 15 subjects.
- **Sampling technique:** Simple randomization
- **Methods of collection of Data** - Data was collected from the subjects using specially prepared case proforma.
- **Dropouts:** No dropouts.
- **Ethical clearance:** Ethical clearance was obtained from the institutional ethics committee (SSIEC/137/2020 dated on 24/04/2020)
- **CTRI registration:** Before commencing the study CTRI registration was done

(Registration number-CTRI/2021/06/034050)

2.2 Inclusion criteria

- Subjects between the age group of 2-5 years were included.
- Subjects with pyrexia presenting with temperature of 99.8°F-103°F (Low-Moderate) were included.
- Subjects of both genders were included irrespective of caste, religion, and socioeconomic status.
- Children whose parents were willing to give consent for the trial.

2.3 Exclusion criteria

- Subjects below 2 years and above 5 years of age were excluded.
- Subjects with chronic systemic diseases were excluded.
- Subjects presenting with high grade fever(>103°F) and hyperpyrexia, with history of febrile seizures, epilepsy, meningitis were excluded.

2.4 Intervention: (Table 1)

30 subjects, diagnosed with *Jwarasantapa* (Pyrexia) were selected and were randomized into 2 groups A & B with 15 subjects each. Group A received *Jwarahara Mahakashya Gudavarti* and Group B received *Amrutottarakashaya Gudavarti* and were assessed at regular intervals.

Table 1: Intervention.

S No	Title	Group A Trial group (15 subjects)	Group B Control group (15 subjects)
1.	Medicine	<i>Jwarahara Mahakashya udavarti</i> (Rectal suppository)	<i>Amrutottara Kashaya Gudavarti</i> (Rectal suppository)
2.	Duration of study	180 minutes	180 minutes
3.	Dose of Medicine	2 g	2 g
4	Frequency of administration of Medicine	Once during the study period	Once during the study period
4.	Assessment Duration (Minutes after administration of the drug)	30 minutes 60 minutes 120 minutes 180 minutes	30 minutes 60 minutes 120 minutes 180 minutes
5.	Rescue medicine	Paracetamol suppository as per subject's body weight	Paracetamol suppository as per subject's body weight

2.5 Method of Preparation

JWARAHARA MAHAKASHAYA GUDAVARTI

(Charaka Chikitsa 4/39)^[4] (Effect of Amrutotharam kashayam as rectal suppository in fever in children aged 2-10 years, 2018)^[9]

Ingredients – 1 Part each of *Sariva* (*Hemidismus indicus* R.Br.), *Patha* (*Cissampelos pareira* Linn), *Manjishta* (*Rubia cordifolia* Linn), *Draksha* (*Vitis vinifera* Linn), *Peelu* (*Salvadora persica* Linn), *Parushaka* (*Grewia asiatica* Linn), *Hareetaki* (*Terminalia chebula* Retz), *Amalaki* (*Embilica officinalis* Gaertn), *Vibheetaki* (*Terminalia bellerica* Roxb), *Sita* (sugar), *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* Miers), *Ghruta*(Ghee) and *Madhucchishta*(Bee wax).

Jwarahara Mahakashaya Gudavarti was prepared by fusion method in 3 stages:

- i. *Jwaraharamahakashaya Ghanasatwa* preparation
- ii. *Guduchi Ghruta* preparation
- iii. *Jwaraharamahakashaya Gudavarti* preparation

(i) ***Jwaraharamahakashaya Ghanasatwa* Preparation.** 100 grams of each of the drugs of *Jwarahara Mahakashaya* except *Sita* were taken and boiled with 8 times of water (7.2 litres) and reduced to $\frac{1}{4}$ (2 litre of *Kashaya*) and filtered and made into a *Ghanasatwa* (**Sargadhara Samhita, Madhyamakhanda 8/1**)^[7] consistency. Thereafter, poured on to a tray & kept in a hot air oven at a low temperature(45-50°C), till it dried. The dried product was then taken and finely powdered (90gms) and preserved in an air tight container. One part of *Sita*(100gm) was powdered and kept in a separate air tight container.

(ii) *Guduchi Ghruta* Preparation

***Guduchi ghruta* preparation (Sargadhara Samhita, Madhyamakhanda 9/3-4)**^[8]-166.67 grams of *Guduchi Kalka* and 4 litres of *Guduchi Kwatha* were added to 1 litre of *Goghruta* and stirred uniformly under medium flame till *Sneha Siddhi lakshana*(*Madhyama paka*) was observed. The obtained *Ghruta* was filtered to a sterile container with the help of cotton cloth and stored in a glass container.

(iii)***Jwaraharamahakashaya Gudavarti* Preparation.** Initially the *Madhucchishta* (Bee wax) (1.5 g) was taken and melted on a low flame & thereafter allowed to cool; into which *Guduchi Ghruta* (12 ml) was then added and uniformly mixed. The measured quantity of the *Ghanasatwa* (15 g) and *Sita* (1.5 g) were then slowly added into the above mixture

and stirred well to attain a homogenous consistency. This mixture was then poured into a metallic pre lubricated mould and allowed to solidify in a refrigerator at a temperature less than 10°C.^[9] After cooling, it was carefully removed from the mould and suppositories (2g each) were packed in an aluminium foil and stored in an air tight glass container at temp<10° C in the refrigerator.

Control Drug-Amrutottara Kashaya Gudavarti was prepared using the same method. Previous research study was conducted on the control drug (*Amrutottara Kashaya Gudavarti*) and had proven significant effect on pyrexia up to 1 hour after the insertion of *Gudavarti*. (**Effect of Amrutotharam kashayam as rectal suppository in fever in children aged 2-10 years, 2018**).^[9]

2.6 Mode of Administration

- Explained the procedure to parents and the subjects.
- Position of the subjects: The child was made to lie down in left lateral position, with his left leg placed straight and the right leg flexed at the hip and knee joint.
- With a gloved hand, the anal opening of the subject was smeared with *Guduchi Ghruta* with sterile cotton swab for the purpose of lubrication.
- Insert the *Gudavarti* with pointed end first, past the internal sphincter for approx. an inch (**Administration of rectal suppositories in children, 2012**).^[21]

2.7 Assessment Criteria

Assessment was done based on the GRASP FEVER CHART for criteria such as Temperature, Heart Rate, Respiratory rate, CRT and Traffic Light Criteria at regular intervals of 30,60,120 & 180 minute.

Table 2: GRASP Fever Chart (Traffic Light Criteria).

S No	GREEN (Gr-1) (Low Risk)	AMBER (Gr-2) (Intermediate Risk)	RED(Gr-3) (High Risk)
1	Normal colour	Pallor reported by parent/caretaker	• Pale/mottled/ ashen/blue
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responds normally to social cues. • Content/Smiles • Stays awake or awakens quickly Strong normal cry/not crying 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not responding normally to social cues • No smile • Wakes only with prolonged stimulation Decreased activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No response to social cues. • Appears ill to a healthcare professional • Doesn't wake or if roused doesn't stay awake. Weak, high-pitched or

			continuous cry
3		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nasal flaring Tachypnoea RR>50 breaths/ minute (age 6-12 months) RR>40 breaths/minute (age>12 months) Oxygen saturation\leq95% in air Crackles in the chest 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grunting Tachypnoea RR>60 breaths/minute Moderate or severe chest indrawing
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Normal skin and eyes Moist mucous membranes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tachycardia >160 beats/minute- age <1 year >150 beats/minute-age 1-2 years >140 beats/minute-age 2-5 years CRT\geq 3 Seconds Dry mucous membrane Poor feeding in infant Reduced urine output 	Reduced skin turgor
5	None of the amber or red symptoms or signs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Age 3-6 months, temperature \geq 39°C Fever for \geq 5 days Rigors Swelling of a limb or joint Non-weight bearing limb/ not using an extremity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Age<3 months, temperature\geq38°C Non-blanching rash Bulging fontanelle Neck stiffness Status epilepticus Focal neurological signs Focal seizures
6	Normal colour	Pallor reported by parent/caretaker	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pale/mottled/ ashen/blue

Ayurvedic Assessment Criteria

Ayurvedic assessment criteria based on the *Pratyatma Lakshanas (Madhava Nidana,1)*^[10] of *Jwara* was used in the clinical trail. Parameters such as *Sweda Avarodha* (Absence of sweat), *Arati* (Irritability), *Klama* (Exhaustion), *Shaktyabhava* (Weakness), *Sarvanga Grahana* (General body ache), *Anannabhilasha* (Loss of appetite) were monitored at regular intervals of 60,120 & 180 minutes and Scoring was done based on the presence & absence of the symptoms.

Statistical Study (Research methods & techniques, 2004)^[11] (**Methods in biostatistics, 2005**)^[12]

The analysis was carried out using IBM SPSS software version 20. Paired t test, was employed to analyze the objective parameters within the groups. Unpaired t test was

employed to analyze the objective parameters between the groups. Wilcoxon signed rank test was employed to analyze the subjective parameters within the groups and Mann-Whitney U test was employed to analyze the subjective parameters between the groups. After the statistical analysis, interpretation of the results was done based on the Mean value and p value.

3. OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

In the present study, it showed 40% of subjects belonged to 2-3years, 30% of subjects belonged to 3.1- 4 years, 30% of subjects belonged to 4.1-5 years. 100% of subjects had *Dehasantapa* (Increased body temperature). 63.44% of subjects had the difficulty of *Sarvangagrahana* (General body aches). 100% of the subjects had *Sveda Avarodha* (Absence of sweat). 80% of subjects had the difficulty of *Arati* (irritability). 83.33% of subjects had the difficulty of *Shrama* (Tiredness). 73.33% of subjects had the difficulty of *Anannabhilasha* (Poor appetite). 100% of subjects had acute onset of fever. 40% of subjects had low grade fever, 33.33% of subjects had mild grade fever and 26.67% of subjects had moderate grade fever. In the present study, 56.67% of subjects had the habit of *Sheetala Ahara Sevana*(cold food intake). 36.67% of subjects had the habit of intake of fast-food/outdoor food and meals (*Guru Asatmya Anna Sevana*). 13.33% of subjects had the habit of intake of *Dadhi*(Curd intake). 26.67% of subjects had the habit of intake of Nonvegetarian food. 6.67% of subjects had the habit of *Atyambhupana* (Excess intake of water). 56.67% of subjects had the habit of *Adhyasana*. In the present study, 50% of subjects had presented with *Aruchi*, 33.33% of subjects had presented with *Jrumbha* and 16.67% of subjects had presented with *Daha*.

Table 3: Grasp fever chart criteria-showing the effect within the group.

	Group						Mean Diff				P Value				Inference			
		BT	30 min	60 min	120 min	180 min	30 min	60 min	120 min	180 min	30 Min	60 min	120 min	180 min	30 min	60 min	120 min	180 min
Temp	A	101.38	100.00	99.17	98.68	98.48	1.38	2.21	2.70	2.89	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	HS	HS	HS	HS
	B	101.00	100.09	99.56	100.01	100.53	0.91	1.44	0.99	0.47	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.005	HS	HS	HS	HS
HR	A	136.93	126.27	136.93	116.13	112.93	10.67	17.33	20.80	24.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	HS	HS	HS	HS
	B	135.87	130.26	135.87	127.73	132.00	5.60	12.20	8.13	13.87	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.010	HS	HS	HS	S
RR	A	35.06	31.53	29.20	27.47	26.67	3.53	5.87	7.60	8.40	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	HS	HS	HS	HS
	B	34.53	32.53	30.13	31.27	33.53	2.00	4.40	3.27	1.00	0.001	0.000	0.001	0.218	HS	HS	HS	NS
CRT	A	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	0	0	0	0	-	-	-	-	NS	NS	NS	NS
	B	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	0	0	0	0	-	-	-	-	NS	NS	NS	NS
NICE Traffic System	A	1.80	1.67	1.40	1.20	1.20	0.13	0.40	0.60	0.60	0.16	0.009	0.000	0.000	NS	HS	HS	HS
	B	1.60	1.53	1.27	1.27	0.13	0.07	0.33	0.33	0.13	0.33	0.019	0.019	0.164	NS	S	S	NS

Table 4: Grasp fever chart criteria-showing the effect between the group.

	Group					Mean Diff			P Value			Inference		
		BT	60 min	120 min	180 min	60 min	120 min	180 min	60 Min	120 min	180 min	60 min	120 min	180 min
<i>Sveda Avarodha</i>	A	2.00	1.87	1.73	1.60	0.13	0.27	0.40	0.157	0.046	0.014	NS	S	S
	B	1.80	2.00	2.00	1.93	0	0	0.07	1.000	1.000	0.321	NS	NS	NS
<i>Arati</i>	A	1.80	1.53	1.13	1.00	0.27	1.13	0.80	0.046	0.002	0.001	S	HS	HS
	B	1.67	1.67	1.40	1.60	0.07	1.40	0.07	0.317	0.046	0.655	NS	S	NS
<i>Anannabhilasha</i>	A	1.73	1.73	1.73	1.73	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.000	1.000	1.000	NS	NS	NS
	B	1.73	1.73	1.73	1.73	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.000	1.000	1.000	NS	NS	NS
<i>Klama</i>	A	1.60	1.40	1.40	1.13	0.20	0.20	0.47	0.083	0.180	0.008	NS	NS	HS
	B	1.53	1.33	1.40	1.40	0.20	0.13	0.13	0.083	0.157	1.000	NS	NS	NS
<i>Sarvanga Grahana</i>	A	1.47	1.47	1.47	1.20	0.00	0.00	0.27	1.000	1.000	0.046	NS	NS	S
	B	1.40	1.40	1.40	1.33	0.00	0.00	0.07	1.000	1.000	0.317	NS	NS	NS
<i>Shaktyabhava</i>	A	1.33	1.33	1.13	1.00	0.00	0.20	0.33	1.000	0.083	0.025	NS	NS	S
	B	1.27	1.27	1.27	1.27	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.000	1.000	1.000	NS	NS	NS

Table 5: Ayurvedic assessment criteria-showing the effect within the group.

	Group						Inference									
		BT	30 min	60 min	120 min	180 min	BT	30 min	60 Min	120 min	180 min	BT	30 min	60 min	120 min	180 min
Temp	A	101.38	100.00	99.17	98.68	98.48	0.375	0.813	0.290	0.000	0.000	NS	NS	NS	HS	HS
	B	101.00	100.09	99.56	100.01	100.53										
HR	A	136.93	126.27	119.60	116.13	112.93	0.741	0.173	0.230	0.001	0.000	NS	NS	NS	HS	HS
	B	135.87	130.27	123.67	127.73	132.00										
RR	A	35.07	31.53	29.20	27.47	26.67	0.640	0.255	0.338	0.000	0.000	NS	NS	NS	HS	HS
	B	34.53	32.53	30.13	31.27	33.53										
CRT	A	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	-	-	-	-	-	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
	B	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	2.00										
NICE Traffic System	A	1.80	1.67	1.40	1.20	1.20	0.247	0.473	0.456	0.679	0.130	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
	B	1.60	1.53	1.27	1.27	1.47										

Table 6: Ayurvedic assessment criteria-showing the effect between the group.

	Group	Mean Rank				P value				Inference			
		BT	60 min	120 min	180 min	BT	60 min	120 min	180 min	BT	60 Min	120 min	180 min
<i>Sveda Avarodha</i>	A	15.50	14.50	13.50	13.00	1.000	0.150	0.035	0.034	NS	NS	S	S
	B	15.50	16.50	17.50	18.00								
<i>Arati</i>	A	16.50	14.00	13.50	11.00	0.417	0.264	0.104	0.000	NS	NS	NS	HS
	B	17.00	14.50	17.50	20.00								
<i>Annabhilasha</i>	A	15.50	15.50	15.50	15.50	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	NS	NS	NS	NS
	B	15.50	15.50	15.50	15.50								
<i>Klama</i>	A	16.00	16.00	15.50	12.50	0.717	0.710	1.000	0.022	NS	NS	NS	S
	B	15.00	15.00	15.50	18.50								
<i>Sarvanga Grahana</i>	A	16.00	16.00	16.00	14.50	0.717	0.717	0.717	0.417	NS	NS	NS	NS
	B	15.00	15.00	15.00	16.50								
<i>Shakti abhava</i>	A	16.00	16.00	14.50	13.50	0.695	0.695	0.369	0.035	NS	NS	NS	S
	B	15.00	15.00	16.50	17.50								

After the statistical analysis, interpretation of the result was done based on the p value and mean value. The data within the group and between the group of **GRASP Fever Chart** were analyzed and the same areas under:

- **Jwarasantapa** - Highly significant effect was observed with respect to *Jwara santapa*(Pyrexia) at 30min., 60min,120min and 180 minutes of treatment in group A & B with a p value of 0.000,0.000,0.000,0.000 & 0.000,0.000,0.000,0.005 respectively. While comparing the same between the groups, Group A with a lower mean value of 98.68 and 98.48 was more effective at 120 minutes and 180 minutes.
- **Heart Rate** - Highly significant effect was observed with respect to Heart Rate at 30minutes, 60minutes, 120minutes and 180 minutes of treatment in group A with a p value of 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000 & highly significant effect at 30minutes, 60minutes, 120minutes of treatment in group B with a p value 0.000 and significant effect at 180minutes with a p value of 0.010. While comparing the same between the groups Group A with a lower mean value of 116.13 and 112.93 was more effective at 120 minutes and 180 minutes.
- **Respiratory Rate** - Highly significant effect was observed with respect to Respiratory Rate at 30 min., 60 min, 120 min. and 180 minutes of treatment in group A with a p value of 0.000 & highly significant effect was observed in group B at 30 minutes, 60 minutes, 120 minutes with a p value of 0.001, 0.000, 0.001 and no significant effect was observed at 180 minutes with a p value 0.218. While comparing the same between the groups, Group A with a lower mean value of 27.47 and 26.67 was more effective at 120 minutes and 180 minutes.
- **Capillary refill Time (CRT)** - No significant effect was observed within & between the groups.
- **NICE Traffic Light System Criteria** - Highly significant effect was observed with respect to NICE Traffic Light System criteria at 60 minues, 120 minutes and 180 minutes of treatment in group A with a p value of 0.009, 0.000, 0.000 respectively & significant effect was observed at 60minutes and 120 minutes with a p value of 0.019 and no significant effect at 180 minutes in group B with a p value 0.164. While comparing the same between the groups & within the group, both the groups were equally significant.

Similarly, the data within the group and between the group of **Ayurvedic Assessment Criteria** were analyzed and the same are as under:

- **Sveda Avarodha** - Significant effect was observed with respect to *Sveda Avarodha* at 60 minutes and 180 minutes of treatment in group A with a p value of 0.046 and 0.014 respectively & no significant effect was observed in group B with a p value 0.317. While comparing the same between the groups, Group A with a lower mean rank (13.00) was more effective at 180 minutes.
- **Arati** - Highly significant effect was observed with respect to *Arati* at 120 minutes and 180 minutes of treatment in group A with a p value of 0.002 and 0.001 respectively & significant effect was observed in group B at 120 minutes with a p value of 0.046 and no significant effect in group B with a p value 0.655 at 180 minutes. While comparing the same between the groups, Group A with a lower mean rank of 11 was more effective at 180 minutes.
- **Anannabhilasha** - No significant effect was observed with respect to *Anannabhilasha* at 180 minutes of treatment within & between the groups A & B.
- **Klama** - Highly significant effect was observed with respect to *Klama* at 180 minutes of treatment in group A with a p value of 0.008 & no significant effect in group B with a p value 1.000. While comparing the same between the groups, Group A with a lower mean rank (12.50) was more effective at 180 minutes.
- **Sarvangagrahana** - Significant effect was observed with respect to *Sarvangagrahana* at 180 minutes of treatment in group A with a p value of 0.046 & no significant effect in group B with a p value 0.317. While comparing the same between the groups, Group A with a lower mean rank of 16.50 was more effective at 180 minutes.
- **Shaktyi Abhava** - Significant effect was observed with respect to *Shakti Abhava* at 180 minutes of treatment in group A with a p value of 0.025 & no significant effect in group B with a p value 1.000. While comparing the same between the groups, Group A with a lower mean rank of 13.50 was more effective.

3.1 Characterization Study

The prepared medicine was subjected to physical and chemical characterization studies namely XRD, SEM and ZETA potential at.

CeNSE in Indian Institute of Science, Bengaluru. The results obtained are as under: -

- **SEM (Scanning electron microscope)**- Mean weight percentage of the elemental

components in the sample (*Jwarahara Ghanasatwa* powder) are Carbon(C) is present with (55.26%), Oxygen(O) is present with 41.40%, Sodium (Na) is present with 0.41%, Magnesium is present with 0.17%, Silicon (Si) is present with 0.39%, Chlorine (Cl) is present with 0.81%, Potassium(K) is present with 1.61%, Calcium is present with 0.12%, Aluminium is present with 0.38% and Gold (Au) with a percentage of 0.00%.

- **ZETA potential-** The particle size of the *Ghanasatwa* is 300nm. The negative sign indicates that the charge on the surface of the individual particle is negative. As the zeta potential value is -15.98 mV, it shows the particles are less stable in the solvent.
- **XRD** - No sharp peaks were observed in both XRD powder (*Ghanasatwa*) and XRD thin film (*Gudavarti*). Crystalline peaks superimposed on a broad peak centred at $\sim 21^\circ$ are observed.

4. DISCUSSION

- ***Jwara Santapa*** - Group A contains drugs which has *Sheeta Guna* and *Sheeta Veerya*. *Amalaki, Guduchi, Patha, Parushaka* have proven antipyretic action. They contain the phytochemicals like flavonoid, glycosidic flavonoids, Amino acids, salicylates etc. which reduce prostaglandin levels thereby reduce the hypothalamic temperature set point to lower levels resulting in reduction of temperature. *Jwaraharamahakashya* drugs combination has proven reduction of PGE2 by 13.19% (**Antipyretic effect of a traditional polyherbal preparation, 2008**)^[13] This sustained effect in Group A is probably because it contains more *Sheeta Guna* and *Sheeta Veerya Dravyas* or because of the proven long-lasting antipyretic activity (**Antipyretic activity of Guduchi ghruta, 2010**)^[14] of *Guduchi Ghruta*.
- **Heart Rate & Respiratory Rate** - The heartrate reduces approximately by 10b/minutes when the body temperature reduces by 1°F (**Pediatric clinical examination, 2014**)^[15] The drugs in *Jwaraharamahakashaya*, have proven effect in the inhibition of PGE2, thus reducing the contraction frequency of heart and heartrate during fever episode. The *Dehasantapa* is because of the increase in *Rookshatejas* which also vitiates the *Vyanavayu* increasing the *Hridgati*(Heart rate). The *Jwarahara Mahakashaya Gudavarti* reduces *Ushnata* by its *Sheeta guna*. It renders *Snigdhatata* by the presence of *Guduchi Ghruta*, thus controlling *Vyanavayu* vitiation and reducing the heart rate. Similarly in case if respiratory rate, it reduces by 4 cycles/ minute (**Pediatric clinical examination, 2014**)^[15].
- **CRT** - CRT was normal in all subjects probably due to the absence of marked

dehydration. Both groups were effective in reducing the temperature, preventing dehydration and prevented the occurrence of prolonged CRT.

- **NICE Traffic System Criteria** - The activity level improved in both the groups due to the decrease in metabolic rate and energy consumption as the temperature got reduced.
- **Sveda Avarodha** - The drugs that is guru *Sara Guna*, *Katu Rasa* helps in *Vilayata Roopa vrudhi* of Adhered *Kapha* in *Svedhavaahasrotas*(*Bahirmugha srotas*) and the drugs like *Patha*, *Vibheetaki*, *Manjishta*, *Guduchi* etc by their *Ushna*, *Teekshna guna* helps in *Paka*(liquefaction) of the *Vrudha Kapha* and there by releases *Avarana* in *Srotas* and facilitates its movement in circulation. *Triphala*, *Manjishta* and *Guduchighruta* help in controlling *Vatadosha* by enhancing the *Mootrala* action and there by release the *Avarodha* and by the *Prabhava* of *Sariva*, *Parushaka* and *Patha* helps in *Sweda Pradurbhava* in *Bahirmugha srotas*, thus produce perspiration in subjects. More number of *Guru Sara Guna Dravyas* and the presence of *Swedajanana Dravyas* in Group A may probably be the reason for an increased effectiveness in group A.
- **Klama** - *Jwaraharamahakashaya* had sustained effect in reducing *Jwara santapa* there by further *Soshana* of *Ojus* was prevented and to some extend the stability of *Ojus* was established. *Madhura*, *Snigdha*, *Sheetala Pradhana Dravyas* of *Jwarahara Mahakashaya* helped in reducing *Klama*. Due to the reduction of body temperature, increased need of energy and metabolic rate got reduced and in turn exhaustion of body. The presence of *Sarkara* (sugar) and with higher number of *Madhura Rasa* and *Snigdha Guna Dravya* and optimized action of *Ghruta* as base may be the reason for a significance at 180 minutes in Group A.
- **Shakti Abhava** - Group A was effective in reducing *Klama* at 180 minutes, so there was a relative improvement in *Karma sadhana shakti* at 180 minutes which was absent in Group B.
- **Anannabhilasha** - *Anannabhilasha* was due to the displacement of *Agni* from *Aamashaya* and presence of *Aama*. Though the *Gudavarti* helped in reduction of *Jwarasanatapa*, the *Agnideepana* and *Aamapachana* was not achieved as *Vartis* did not act on *Jatharagni* directly. As a result, both the groups failed to reduce *Anannabhilasha*.
- **Sarvangagrahana** - *Sarvangagrahana* or *Stambha* is due to *Avarodha* of *Antarmukha srotas* which obstructs the movement of *Vata*. *Jwaraharamahakashaya gudavarti* was to some extend (18.18%) able to relieve the *Sanga* of *Antarmukha srotas* at 180 minutes. Most probably due to the *Ushna Teekshna Guna* of *Hareetaki*, *Patha*, *Manjishta*,

Vibheetaki. The ingredients, *Sariva*, *Manjishta*, *Parushaka*, *Vibheetaki*, *Amalaki* have proven Analgesic activity, which may reduce the pain perception. *Amrutottara varti* was not effective in relieving *Antarmukha Srotosanga* thus had no effect on *Sarvangagrahana*.

- **Arati** - *Arati* is a *Manasantapa lakshana* caused by *Rajoguna vrudhi*. The bodily suffering like *Santapa*, *Klama*, *Sarvanga Grahana* causes *Arati* in *Jwara*. Since *Gudavarti* were effective in reducing the above symptoms, they indirectly led to the reduction of *Arati*.

4.1 Concomitant medicine: Paracetamol suppository as per the body weight of subjects were planned as the concomitant medicine (Rescue medicine), but none of the subjects have received the concomitant drug during the study, as there was a relative decrease in the temperature after the administration of *Gudavartis*.

4.2 Probable Mode of Action

In Group A, *Jwarahara Mahakashaya Gudavarti* consists of *Jwaraharamahakashaya Ghanasatwa* powder (Drug) which is hydrophilic in nature mixed with *Guduchi Ghruta* as base which is lipophilic in nature and *Madhucchishta* as a solidifying agent which are the essentials for an ideal suppository. The hydrophilic property of drug helps it to get dissolved in the rectal fluid and lipophilic nature of base helps it to cross the epithelium of rectum.

After insertion of *Gudavarti*, in the rectal cavity it tends to melt and spread. Due to the hydrophilic nature of drug, it gets dissolved in the luminal fluid and is absorbed. Because of the lipophilic nature of base *Gudavarti* readily melts at high body temperature and release drug on the mucosal surface and transcellular diffusion will take place along with paracellular diffusion. The ideal qualities of suppository bases are (**The science and practice of pharmacy, 2012**)^[20] - Should easily attain the shape of mould, base should melt/dissolve in rectum, Base should be stable during storage, should not irritate the rectal mucosa etc. *Guduchi Ghruta* satisfied all the qualities of ideal suppository base.

When the *Gudavarti* melts onto mucosal surface, the drug molecule diffuses and enters the rectal venous plexus which is in the submucosa of rectum. Since the *Varti* was inserted into the lower part of the rectum, the action was quicker, this was because, the inferior and middle rectal vein from the lower and middle part of rectum drain to internal iliac vein and then to common iliac vein and to inferior venacava, which will bypass the first pass metabolism and

directly enter into systemic circulation. From here the drug enters the anterior cerebral and anterior communicating arteries and reach the preoptic center (thermoregulatory center) of hypothalamus. During fever episode, the pyrogens produce prostaglandins in the anterior hypothalamus which results in setting of thermoregulatory point at higher level. *Jwarahara Mahakashaya* contains flavonoids and subtypes of flavonoids which has proven to reduce Prostaglandin E₂(PGE₂) up to 13.19% (**Antipyretic effect of a traditional polyherbal preparation, 2008**)^[13], which in turn reduces the raised body temperature by setting the hypothalamic temperature set point to normal limit. In addition, *Guduchi Ghruta* also contains flavonoids which has an added benefit in reduction of prostaglandin release, which improved the effectiveness of the Suppository and resulted in the sustained action (**Antipyretic activity of Guduchi Ghruta, 2010**)^[14] on *Jwarasantapa* till 180 minutes of treatment.

In addition to the nature of drugs and base the particle size also plays a role in the efficacy of the drug because, absorption of drug largely depends on the particle size. Smaller particle will have better absorption rates and in an ideal suppository the particle size of the drug should be <50 μm (**Rectal suppository as an effective alternative for oral administration, 2006**)^[16] The particle size of the *Jwaraharamahakashaya Ghanasatwa* is 300nm, which is much smaller than the required particle size ie 50 μm , hence it exponentially increases the absorption rate of medicine through an easy and faster paracellular diffusion and transcellular diffusion. The mean Zeta potential value of the *Ghanasatwa* (Drug part is -15.98 mv, which indicated it has a lesser stability in the solvent(water). This helped in the easy dissolution of the drug in the rectal fluid and quicker absorption. Thus, the nature of the drug and the base, drug composition, particle size, site of insertion of *Varti* facilitated an easy dissolution of the drug and quicker absorption rendering a systemic effect of antipyretic action.

Jwarasantapa is mainly due to increased *Ushnaguna* of *Pitta*. Along with aggravated *Vatadosha*, *Ushnaguna* of *Pitta* is carried all over the body produces *Jwarasantapa* in *Sarvashareera*. During *Jwarasantapa* there is an increase in *Agnitvatva* (temperature) and decrease in *Apa amsa* (water content) in *Shareera*. This increased *Jalalpata* (reduction of hydration) in *Shareera* will further increase the *Jwarasantapa* in the body and in children this is very rapid and severe, as they generally have less water content in the body. This is evidenced in scanty urine. Therefore, while treating *Jwarasantapa*, *Vatasyopakrama*

(treatment to reduce *Vata*) also play an equal role in bringing down the increased *Doshas* to normalcy.

Jwarahara mahakashaya Gudavarti probably by its *Ushnaveerya Dravyas* like *Hareetaki*, *Patha*, *Manjishta*, *Vibheetaki* and *Guduchi* along with *Snigdha Guna* of *Ghruta*, can easily melt and dissolves in the *Guda*, *Basti Pradesha* and *Pakwasaya* and get absorbed quickly into the *Udakavaha Srotas* through the multiple invisible *Ambuvahini* present in *Basti* and *Pakwasaya* (which are the *Mooladhara* for *Mootrasaya*). The *Ushnaveerya* of *Gudavarti* had helped in pacification of *Prakupita Vatadosha* from its *Moola* and thereby prevents the further spread of *Ushnaguna* of *Pittadosha*. The drugs of *Gudavarti* i.e *Amalaki*, *Peelu*, *Draksha*, *Sariva*, *Parushaka* and *Ghruta* had *Sheetaveerya* in property probably helped in reducing *Ushnata* of *Pitta* in *Sarvasareera*, when get absorbed into *Udakavahasrotas*. The *Veerya* of these drugs also did *Tarpana*(nourishment) of the *Ap Mahabhoota* by their *Madhura*, *Snigdha* property and enhanced *Jaleeya amsa* in the extracellular and intracellular compartment of body and the intensity of *Jwarasantapa* got reduced. Probably by the *Ushnaveerya* property of the drugs when got absorbed, helped in releasing the *Avarodha* (Obstruction) of *Swedavaha Srotas* caused by *Kupita Kapha* and facilitated *Swedapradurbhava*(Production of sweat) by the *Prabhava* of *Sweda janana dravayas* i.e *Sariva*, *Parushaka* and *Patha* resulted in reduction of *Jwara Santapa*(**Charaka Sidhi 9/4**)^[17] (**Charaka Sidhi 11/33**)^[18] (**Susruta Sidhi 11/33**).^[19]

The *Gudavarti* acted by their *Veerya* and helped in pacification of *Doshas* from *Apatatalamoordha*(all over the body from head to toe) as said in classics was observed in *Jwaraharamahakashaya Gudavarti* in subjects, where the drug could maintain *Avegavasta* of *Jwarasantapa* for 180 minutes with relative reduction of *Dehasantapa* with a mean difference of 2.89°F.

5. CONCLUSION

On statistical analysis, both medicines were found to be effective within Group A and B. When comparing the effect of treatment in between the groups, highly significance in P value was noticed in 5 out of 11 parameters of assessment criteria and the effect of treatment was found to be more effective in Group A, 4 out of 11 parameters are found to be equally effective in both group A and B and 2 out of 11 parameters are found to be equally not effective in both Group A and B. *Jwarahara Mahakashaya Gudavarti* and *Amrutottarakashaya Gudavarti* were almost equally effective till 60 minutes. *Jwarahara*

Mahakashaya Gudavarti had sustained action up to 180 minutes w.r. t to *Jwarasantapa*(Figure-1).

Figure 1: Showing the effect of group A and Group B w.r t to *Jwarasantapa* (Pyrexia).

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